

Example Data Management Plan – complete version with full responses

Predicting health risks from genomic, environmental and lifestyle factors using machine learning

Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW) Example Data Management Plan

Complete version with full responses

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Based on

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(Q1) Proposal name

Predicting health risks from genomic, environmental and lifestyle factors using machine learning.

(Q2) Description of the data: Type of study

This will integrate genomic, environmental and lifestyle data to understand and predict health risk factors using Machine Learning.

(Q3) Description of the data: Types of data

Quantitative data of 3 different types will be used:

1. **Genomic Data:** Whole genome sequencing (WGS) data, including single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) and other genetic variations.
2. **Environmental Data:** Information on air quality, water quality, and exposure to various environmental pollutants.
3. **Lifestyle Data:** Data on physical activity, diet, smoking status, alcohol consumption, and sleep patterns.

(Q4) Description of the data: Origin of the data

New quantitative data will be generated from the study participants for Whole Genome Sequencing (WGS). Samples (e.g., blood or saliva) for sequencing will be collected from study participants. Environmental Data on air quality, water quality, and exposure to pollutants will be obtained from governmental and international organisations (e.g., EPA, WHO). Lifestyle Data will be collected from participants using Surveys and Questionnaires and Wearable Devices (e.g., Fitbit, Apple Watch) for objective measurements of physical activity, sleep duration and quality.

(Q5) Description of the data: Format and scale of the data

For WGS, raw sequencing data will be in the form of FASTQ files containing the raw sequencing reads, which will then be aligned to the reference genome and saved as BAM files. Files with annotations such as SNPs will be saved as VCF (Variant Call Format). This data will be approximately 200 GB per individual. The study will be conducted on 50 individuals, amounting to 10 TB of data.

Environmental Data will be tabular data stored in CSV, Excel, or database tables containing environmental measurements (e.g., air quality indices, pollutant levels). Lifestyle data from surveys will be in CSV or Excel files containing self-reported information and data

from wearable devices will be in JSON or proprietary formats from device manufacturers. This will be in the range of 500 GB.

(Q6) Managing, storing and curating data

Initially, data will be stored on the central computational facility provided by the Research IT at the University, which is backed up and snapshots are taken every 24 hrs to mitigate the data loss risk. All the analysis of the raw data will also be carried out on the central computational facility accessed via encrypted user accounts assigned by the IT. We will request more computational power and storage from Research IT. This will be in addition to our usual subscription with the Research IT and will require an additional surcharge. Relational databases (e.g. MySQL) will be used to store encrypted participant information, survey responses, and processed genomic variant data.

In the longer term, after publication, data will be submitted to public repositories, e.g. European Nucleotide Archive (ENA), PANGAEA and Zenodo. Each dataset will be assigned a global unique identifier (accession number) which can be used in future references. Appropriate metadata will be associated with both raw and processed data.

All personal information regarding the participants will be encrypted in accordance with GDPR and other required policies. Role-based access control (RBAC) to restrict data access to authorised personnel only will be implemented.

(Q7) Metadata standards and data documentation

Genomic data will be annotated in compliance with the ENA metadata model. For environmental data we will follow ISO 19115, a standard for describing geographic information and services, including environmental data.

For lifestyle data, we will use HL7 FHIR (Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources), a standard for exchanging healthcare information electronically, suitable for lifestyle and clinical data. CDISC (Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium) standards, useful for structured lifestyle data collection will also be used.

(Q8) Data preservation strategy and standards

All raw data and processed data generated will be stored on the central computational facility of the university.

The WGS data will also be made available via the public repository, ENA (ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/home). All environmental and lifestyle-related data will be stored in platforms like PANGAEA, and Lifestyle Data will be shared via Zenodo. Analysis pipelines (e.g. Jupyter notebooks) will also be made available on Zenodo. Machine Learning models will be shared on public platforms (e.g. GitHub or HuggingFace).

We will keep all important research data, along with the metadata for at least 10 years, following the guidelines set by the BBSRC for maintaining high standards in scientific work.

(Q9) Where will data be shared?

All raw data (FASTQ) and processed data generated from WGS experiments will be made available via the public repository, ENA. ENA assigns a unique identifier called Accession Number to each dataset.

All environmental and lifestyle-related data will be stored in platforms like PANGAEA, and Lifestyle Data will be shared via Zenodo. Analysis pipelines (e.g. Jupyter notebooks) will also be made available on Zenodo.

Machine Learning models will be shared on public platforms (e.g. GitHub or HuggingFace). All models are assigned a DOI.

(Q10) When will data be available?

Data will be made immediately available after the paper is accepted for publication.

(Q11) How will data be made findable and accessible?

All raw (FASTQ) and processed data generated from WGS experiments will be made available via the public repository, ENA. ENA assigns an accession number to all datasets, which is a unique identifier for the dataset. Comprehensive metadata standards such as MINSEQE, ISO 19115, and HL7 FHIR will be employed for all the data generated or used.

Machine Learning models shared on public platforms (e.g. GitHub or HuggingFace) will have a DOI assigned to them.

All environmental and lifestyle-related data will be stored in platforms like PANGAEA, and Lifestyle Data will be shared via Zenodo. Analysis pipelines (e.g. Jupyter notebooks) will also be made available on Zenodo.

(Q12) How will data be made reusable?

Metadata required for appropriate reuse and interoperable data formats will accompany all data submitted to the public repository, ENA (ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/home). Comprehensive metadata standards such as ISO 19115, for environmental data and HL7 FHIR for lifestyle data will also be employed.

Appropriate metadata following the DOME-ML and Open Neural Network Exchange (ONNX) recommendations will be provided with the ML models. Input data will be shared with metadata on OpenML.

Analysis pipelines (e.g. jupyter notebooks) will also be made available on Zenodo. Detailed methodology about data preparation and analysis will also be provided in the methodology and supplementary methodology of the publication.

(Q13) Restrictions or delays to sharing, with planned actions to limit such restrictions

We do not expect any delays or deviations. No restrictions will be placed on the data. Participant information will be appropriately anonymised and encrypted in accordance with GDPR laws.

(Q14) Secondary use

All raw and analysed data will be made available to researchers for secondary analysis. Participant data will be anonymised to protect identities.

(Q15) Formal information/data security standards

Not Applicable

(Q16) Main risks to data security

All personal information regarding the participants will be encrypted in accordance with GDPR laws. The participants will be given a unique pseudonymised ID, which will be used as their identifier. The mapping between the pseudonymised ID and identifiable participant information (including name and address) will be managed by authorised personnel only.

To achieve this, Role-based access control (RBAC) to restrict data access to authorised personnel only will be implemented.

(Q17) Capabilities

Raw, intermediate and analysed data will all be stored and curated on the Computational infrastructure provided by the Research IT of the university. The university provides a secure, replicated data store supported by university staff.

There is no specific support for data management and all responsibilities will be looked after by the researchers themselves.

(Q18) Maintaining and implementing the Data Management Plan

Given the scale of the data generated and collected, DMP will be crucial for the success of this study. The DMP will be regularly evaluated and updated as per requirements. It will remain a live document throughout the lifecycle of the project.

(Q19) Environmental considerations

The University is committed to zero direct carbon emissions by 2038 and has taken various measures to achieve that. It uses the Laboratory Efficiency Assessment Framework (LEAF) guidance framework to improve the sustainability and efficiency of research and laboratory spaces.